

FAIR Software Route Landscaping

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Introduction

The *FAIR Software Route* project is a joint initiative of DANS & NLeSC which aims at establishing an *online guide* supporting researchers to publish and preserve their research software for the long term in an appropriate repository following the FAIR principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The *FAIR Software Route online guide* will be also part of a more comprehensive resource (research-software.nl) providing information on coding best practices, software reuse, and training. A crucial step in building the *FAIR Software Route* online guide is to canvas the landscape of infrastructure providers in the field of software development, publication, storage and long term preservation. This exercise will capture information about existing projects, the role they play, and how they fit into a *FAIR Software Route*. The landscaping is also an aid to identify gaps in current practices and provide recommendations for the *FAIR Software Route*.

From FAIR Data to FAIR Software

The landscape of infrastructure for research data sharing and preservation changed significantly over the last years to meet information technology developments and also to meet the requirements stipulated by the Open Science concept defined by researchers¹, funders² and policy makers³. Central to this framework are the principles of accessibility, accountability and sustainability in the process of management, dissemination and stewardship of research outputs which include data and also increasingly software as a critical element for the interpretation and reuse of data. In this evolving landscape and cultural context, several instruments were developed to align digital research practices with the framework of Open Science. The focus was initially on open access to publications, later it shifted to research data and more recently to software.

¹ National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. 2018. Open Science by Design: Realizing a Vision for 21st Century Research. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/25116>

² Commission Recommendation (EU) 2018/790 of 25 April 2018 on access to and preservation of scientific information <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018H0790>

³ OECD (2015), "Making Open Science a Reality", OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, No. 25, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/5jrs2f963zs1-en>

The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship⁴ are one of these vehicles developed as a set of high level aspirational principles describing four characteristics (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) that datasets, tools (including software) and vocabularies should exhibit enabled by appropriate infrastructures. These principles do not come with details about the practical implementation and assessment, however, several efforts to develop FAIR metrics are ongoing⁵. These principles are well recognized in the data management and stewardship community and are increasingly recognized by the researchers community.

The FAIR Principles are also frequently used as a benchmark to develop and improve research data infrastructure to maximize the reuse of scholarly data. They are also increasingly used to define the practical requirements for sustainable and “FAIR” software. Although the FAIR principles are high-level aspirational guidelines, they have nevertheless a data-centric approach and were formulated with this context in mind. Software can be generally considered as a special kind of “executable” data or even as an aid for data generation, representation and processing. From a preservation and sustainability perspective, its stewardship requires very specialized technologies and has many dependencies such as requiring specific hardware to run, a specific operating system, specific software libraries to be installed, etc. Consequently, some of the FAIR Principles can easily be transposed to software and others cannot be transposed as easily and need to be reinterpreted in this special context in particular regarding practical requirements, implementation and assessment. Efforts to map the FAIR Principles to software requirements are currently in progress⁶. Similarly, recommendations for good software practices aligned and inspired by FAIR Principles are also published⁷ or being developed^{8,9}.

FAIR Software in FAIR Repositories

The FAIR Principles are also relevant to research data repositories because they are an essential component of the data infrastructure providing the long term preservation and

⁴ Wilkinson, M. D. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* 3:160018 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁵ Wilkinson, M. D. et al. A design framework and exemplar metrics for FAIRness. *Sci. Data* 5:180118 (2018) <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.118>

⁶ Summary of Making software FAIR workshop during DTL Communities@Work 2018, https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Sb7h1NhtuMvIvX7H8tmtOt-ES_jFp49MyI4DL1IL6Pw/edit#heading=h.yudg992puiv3

⁷ Four simple recommendations to encourage best practices in research software: <https://doi.org/10.12688/F1000RESEARCH.11407.1>

⁸ Top 10 FAIR Data Things: Research Software: <http://librarycarpentry.org/Top10FAIR/03-software/>

⁹ CLARIAH Software Quality Guidelines: <https://github.com/CLARIAH/software-quality-guidelines/blob/master/softwareguidelines.pdf>

stewardship functions. The *CoreTrustSeal Data Repositories Requirements*¹⁰ which define the minimum characteristics of trustworthy data repositories applicable in every scientific domain are another instrument geared towards practical implementation of the FAIR principles and assessment of research data repositories. These requirements are defined in alignment with the Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS)¹¹, the international standard for data repositories also known as ISO 14721:2012. The requirements are also mapped to ISO 16363:2012, the international standard for audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories. Trustworthy data repositories such as those meeting the CoreTrustSeal requirements enable the FAIR data, and datasets they hold are managed, curated, and archived in such a way that they remain useful and meaningful into the future.

The OAIS reference model discusses software with a focus on *Representation Rendering Software* and *Access Software*. For Access Software (software providing access to services, such as displaying, manipulating, processing, or sub-setting, to a Digital Object), it concludes that the OAIS does not need to maintain or provide such software if it is widely available. On the other hand (if it is not widely available), the OAIS may want to maintain and provide this software for more specialized types of Digital Objects and therefore potentially requiring preservation actions.

*“The OAIS response to preserving an Access Software application would likely depend, in large part, on whether or not it had or could obtain the source code for the Access Software. Subsection 5.2.2.1 discusses proven methodologies for preserving application access across changes in technology. **The major factors in the use of these techniques would be the cost/benefit ratio to the OAIS and the associated Designated Community.** If source code or commercial bridges are not available and there is an absolute requirement for the OAIS to preserve the Access look and feel, the OAIS would have to pursue ‘emulation’ technology that is currently being researched in the Digital Library domain. This technology is discussed briefly in 5.2.2.2.”*

The OAIS Reference Model recognizes that preserving working software is much harder than to preserve information in digital forms (for example ZIP Libraries¹²) and discusses possible strategies for e.g. making the source code available, or the use of emulation techniques to preserve working software. The two salient points from the OAIS Reference Model approach

¹⁰ Rorie Edmunds, Hervé L'Hours, Lesley Rickards, Paul Trilsbeek, & Mary Vardigan (2016). Core Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.168411>

¹¹ Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System: OAIS(June 2012) [online] Available at: <https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/650x0m2.pdf>

¹²ZIP File Format (PKWARE) <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/fdd/fdd000354.shtml>

on the role of an OAIS in software preservation (in this case Access Software preservation) are the notions of **widely available software** and **cost/benefit ratio to the OAIS and the associated Designated Community** to preserve the software.

The notion of 'widely available' (or pervasive) software need to be explored in the context of software sustainability. This approach implies that working software is maintained and made available 'outside' of the OAIS and thus that preservation of working software could be a distributed responsibility across multiple actors involved in providing and maintaining infrastructure for software.

Infrastructure providers for software

The first approach to improve understanding of the landscape is to compile a non exhaustive inventory¹³ of known infrastructure providers explicitly offering services for software. The main objective is to identify notable examples to represent and describe the variety of players. While building this inventory it became clear that infrastructure providers respond to different audiences and needs related to software development, sharing and preservation. They play complementary but also sometimes overlapping roles and they can be grouped into three main categories based on their most prominent role: Software Development Platforms, Domain and Community Software Registries, and Software Archives and Repositories. These three groups of infrastructures are interlinked in a complex network of interactions and relationships (See [Figure 1](#): Interactions between Software Developments Platforms, Registries, and Archives.) with the research and software development communities at the centre.

¹³ FAIR Software Route Inventory: <https://qoo.gl/PP3aTs>

Figure 1: Interactions between Software Development and Distribution Platforms, Domain and Community Software Registries, and Software Archives and Repositories.

Software Development Platforms

The first group of infrastructure providers is populated with online platforms hosting collaborative software development and distribution efforts. They have a strong focus on technology, providing technical services enabling software development and publication. They are primarily built to serve the software development communities. These providers are sometimes generic software development, publication and distribution platforms like GitHub or DockerHub which address the needs of multiple communities, or more specialized platforms like PyPI addressing the needs of more specific communities, in this case Python programming language (see Annex. 1).

Code Hosting Platforms

Several code hosting platforms exist, such as GitHub.com, Bitbucket and many others. GitHub.com is probably the most widely used software development platform essentially offering a distributed version controlled source code management service. The platform also enables managing teams, documenting code and other integrated services with other platforms used by the software development communities. However, the sustainability of GitHub.com (free service) is not guaranteed and code repositories created and maintained for free can be removed (or the terms of use changed) without prior notice. This is reason for legitimate concern as this makes the community exposed to a single point of failure.

The services offered by GitHub.com address very well the production and upgrade of source code by teams of developers in a collaborative and controlled environment. These services obviously contribute to ensure the availability of running software in the long term, a mission that aligns very well with the FAIR Principles in particular regarding reusability of code. However, overall the infrastructure is not designed to meet FAIR Principles expectations even if it offers already some compliance and tools to enable them.

For example GitHub.com does not systematically assign a resolvable persistent and unique identifier (PID) to code repositories (**FAIR F1 and F3**). The closest thing available is support for generating URLs as permalinks¹⁴ to a file or snippets of code but this is not systematically used and not persistent, therefore, it does not enable for example referencing and citation in scholarly records. To address this need, GitHub.com recommends the use of third party data archives such as ZENODO or Figshare.com¹⁵ to generate a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for code repositories in particular to address citability of software in scholarly publications. These third party archives and other emerging projects such as Software Heritage concerned with preservation will be discussed in the section on [Software Archives and Repositories](#).

GitHub.com exposes documentation available in code repositories which forms part of what developers are expected to provide to comply with good coding practices. A general description of the software is usually made available in a README.md file in addition to documentation files and also code-level annotations. The information in these files is searchable, however, it is not structured and exposed in a standardized format that could facilitate human and machine discovery. Therefore software metadata available in GitHub.com is not “rich metadata” in a FAIR sense (**F2**) and would need to be complemented, especially in a research context, with structured and standardized domain-relevant metadata

¹⁴ <https://help.github.com/articles/getting-permanent-links-to-files/>

¹⁵ <https://help.github.com/articles/referencing-and-citing-content/>

(R1.2 and R1.3). By definition the software uses a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable coding language but this is not the case for knowledge representation in documentation and the use of vocabularies following FAIR principles is not supported **(I1, I2, I3)**. This layer is particularly important to enable the FAIR Interoperability principles and is often what Domain and Community Software Registries offer (see next section).

Another FAIR principle that GitHub.com meets partially is the indexing of software and metadata in a searchable registry **(F4)** and retrievability of software with its PID using a communication protocol that is standardized, open, free, universally implementable and allowing authentication **(A1, A1.2 and A1.3)**. The GitHub.com registry is indeed searchable and the API¹⁶ made available to retrieve the data meet FAIR requirements. However PIDs are not available and the limits discussed above regarding metadata standards make the use of GitHub.com insufficient to reach sustainability and compliance with FAIR principles..

The preservation for the long term and sustainability (metadata for FAIR Principle **A2.**) is also not covered by GitHub.com which makes no promises on long term availability of code repositories. GitHub allows its users to “archive” a repository which becomes effectively a static project¹⁷ and recommends the use of third party data archives such as ZENODO or Figshare¹⁸ to archive the code repository.

For historical reasons linked to software licensing and open source development, licenses are one aspect of the FAIR Principles **(R1.1.)** that GitHub.com addresses well. Although the platform does not enforce choosing a licence, it does offer a solution for code developers to assign a standardised licence to their code repositories¹⁹.

In conclusion, code hosting platforms exemplified by GitHub.com are really well equipped to enable a FAIR software route but is not addressing all the principles. Its use in a FAIR software route could be recommended but would need to be complemented in a coherent way with additional services in particular to enable discoverability by researchers (Archives and community registries) and ensure the long term availability and reusability of software (Zenodo, Docker and Docker Hub).

¹⁶ <https://developer.github.com/v4/>

¹⁷ <https://help.github.com/articles/about-archiving-repositories/>

¹⁸ <https://help.github.com/articles/referencing-and-citing-content/>

¹⁹ <https://help.github.com/articles/licensing-a-repository/>

Software Distribution Platforms

Software Distribution Platforms support the distribution of software to end users. Examples include Bintray Jfrog which is a software distribution platform that supports several all file formats and offers advanced integration with common development technologies.

Docker is another open platform for developing and running applications enabling developers to package and run applications in a so called container that is independent from the infrastructure environment. Docker also offers a Docker Hub which is a centralized registry for container image discovery hosted on the cloud. It enables distribution, change management, team collaboration, and workflow automation. It allows developers to link to code repositories (such as GitHub.com and others) in order to build, store and link to Docker Cloud to deploy images.

Other software platforms provide services targeted to more specific software development communities. For examples PyPi which is a repository of software for the Python programming language.

From the FAIR Principles perspective, these platforms address to some extent interoperability and reusability of software. Docker technology is for example still dependent on having a mechanism for running docker images. Nevertheless, these platforms provide an added value and are complementary to code hosting platforms such as GitHub.com which are widely used and integrated in Docker Hub²⁰ allowing users to seamlessly generate automated builds.

Domain and Community Software Registries

The second group includes infrastructure providers supplying services designed primarily for groups of researchers for example within a single research domain, an organization or a defined region. These services have a strong focus on enabling discovery, citability and reuse of software by providing researchers with tools to describe, annotate, share and understand the software they produce mostly within their group.

²⁰ <https://docs.docker.com/docker-hub/github/>

Domain registries

The Elixir Tools Platform (See Annex. 1 for details) is a good example in the life sciences and bioinformatics domain that provides the “bio.tools” and “Biocontainers” registries integrated with code hosting and software distribution platforms and technologies.

Elixir Bio.tools is a registry of software tools and data resources which enables searching and accessing life science software. It uses the EDAM ontology for precise tool descriptions, and the “biotoolsSchema” as a description model for the software, which makes it easier for people to find, understand and compare software tools. The software indexed in the registry is described with rich domain specific metadata such as relevant licences, buildability, availability of documentation, contacts and links to scientific publications. In addition it provides links to relevant and authoritative code hosting platforms.

The platform offers also the “Biocontainers” registry which is an open source community-driven framework providing system-agnostic executable environments based on the Docker framework for bioinformatics software. Biocontainers make it easy to share bioinformatics analysis and training software, and make it easier to collaborate with others in developing the software.

The Elixir Tools Platform enable the bioinformatics software developing community to richly document and improve interoperability and reusability of software used by the community, thus addressing most of the FAIR Guiding Principles. For example the platform makes use of internal unique identifiers assigned upon registration of the software but references also other PIDs assigned by an ID-assignment authority other than Bio.tools such as DOIs. Findability and Accessibility are well addressed thanks to the use of an ontology to describe software, links to code hosting repositories and the availability of software deployment packages. However, Bio.tools relies on code hosting platforms and software distribution platforms and technologies to fully deliver its services and this dependency is an issue.

Organisational registries

Some software registries address the needs of specific organizations and the the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) Office of Scientific and Technical Information (OSTI) DOE CODE is an interesting example (See Annex. 1 for details). This software service platform and search tool allows for scientific and business software funded by the organization to be archived and discovered in compliance with US Federal Laws. Software is either deposited on the platform together with minimum metadata and links to an archive or deposited directly on the platform as source code or compiled binary. The main objective of the

platform is to increase discoverability by documenting with minimum metadata and optionally assigning a DOI to the code, making it more easily citable and shared.

In addition to the registry, the OSTI's DOE CODE offers DOE-funded developers and researchers two software/code repository services. Developers can use the GitHub.com OSTI community repository to develop or host open source projects, or use an internal DOE CODE GitLab instance to develop or host projects needing controlled access. The latter option of hosting an organizational Gitlab instance is an interesting strategy to be explored as a possible solution to address the sustainability of code hosting platforms like GitHub.com. In addition to DOE CODE, all US federal agencies are also required to comply with the *Federal Source Code Policy*²¹ and publish their custom code for public access on code.gov, a national software registry requiring compliance with a minimum metadata standard²²

The Netherlands eScience Center (NLeSC) Research Software Directory is another example of an organizational effort to promote sharing and re-use of research software across multiple domains. The Research Software Directory is a curated registry of scientific software building on the integration between GitHub.com and the ZENODO data repository for the assignment of a DOI and linking directly to the code on GitHub.com. Metadata provided is enriched and in most cases more useful than the basic metadata provided in ZENODO. It provides useful context to the software such as links to publications, research projects, organizations and a contact person.

In terms of compliance with FAIR principles, organizational registries like domain registries have a great potential and role to play in supporting discoverability, accessibility and reuse. However, the level to which this is addressed depends greatly on how they are implemented and the efforts put into curating the registries. For example DOE CODE works very well from an organizational perspective to cite software and gain credit (use of DOIs), but the way it is implementing a minimalist metadata compliance presents many limitations for efficient discovery and reusability. NLeSC Research Software Directory on the other hand puts lot of efforts on improving discoverability and reuse but seems to lack the sharpness of a domain registry in describing software.

Software Archives and Repositories

The third group infrastructure providers addressing software includes software archives and repositories with an archival function. This category is only populated with a small group of

²¹ <https://code.gov/policy-guide/introduction>

²² <https://code.gov/about/compliance/inventory-code>

providers offering persistent identifiers, long term availability (bit-level storage) and additional features enabling citation and cross-referencing with scholarly literature. Some archives deal exclusively with software code such as the one of a kind Software Heritage and others as part of a more general data archive remit. The latter group is exemplified by the ZENODO and Figshare.com data repositories expanding their services to software mostly by providing an integration with code hosting platforms.

Research data repositories are increasingly but not sufficiently supporting software deposit for discovery and preservation alongside datasets. Consequently efforts to define minimum and consistent citation and metadata standards for software are only emerging such as the Citation File Format²³ and the CodeMeta Project²⁴.

Some data repositories like ZENODO and Figshare have also implemented an integration with popular software development platforms to harvest published software into their archive and ensure long term availability of the code. These efforts are so far focused on improving citability and discoverability which partly addresses the Findability and Accessibility FAIR principles. DOIs are systematically assigned to versioned resources harvested from code hosting platforms enabling citability. However, metadata available in these repositories are primarily for basic discovery and citability with conformance to schemas such as DataCite and Dublin Core. The overall quality of the metadata is rather poorly addressed as it does neither include nor attempt to enrich or structure the information available in code hosting repositories. Furthermore, direct deposits of code which are slightly better documented with metadata seem marginal compared to harvesting and integration of code from code hosting platforms.

These two repositories do not really address FAIR Interoperability and Reusability principles. They can however be seen as the first steps towards a FAIR Software Route. They must be complemented with appropriate technologies such as software containers and connected with appropriate and relevant platforms to enrich available metadata and ultimately ensure genuine software preservation and sustainability.

The Software Heritage project is the example of an emerging type of software repository built specifically with software in mind, unlike the previous two examples originally built for data and extended for software. The Software Heritage archive harvests en masse source code from publicly available software distribution channels such as version control systems (GitHub, Gitlab, etc.) tarball releases (GNU), and distribution packages (Python Package Index). The mission of the archive is to replicate the source code massively to facilitate its

²³ <https://citation-file-format.github.io/>

²⁴ The CodeMeta Project [online] Available at: <https://codemeta.github.io/>

sharing and ensure its preservation. Basic functionalities of the Software Heritage Archive are already operational in compliance with many of the FAIR Principles. Software is collected and stored following a defined data model, indexed and referenceable with available unique and persistent identifiers the so called intrinsic IDs. The Archive's protocols and technologies are also developed with open source and universally implementable technologies. However, other functionalities are still being worked on such as enabling discovery with full text search, exposing provenance information and curation of the content into meaningful collections.

The Software Heritage Archive in its current state like Zenodo or Figshare does not provide rich and structured metadata about its content. It does captures whatever is available in the source code documentation, annotations or metadata files (for e.g codeMeta.json files) and makes these available in the same form but not searchable. The current focus seems to be on building a foundational universal archive dedicated to software as a digital object with a at a later stage the aim to develop the technology to find, make sense and use its content as part of its development roadmap.

FAIR Software Route

The software landscape is highly dynamic and characterized by high fragmentation. Multiple players are involved and play different roles sometime overlapping or competing and sometimes complementing their mutual services and functionalities. This situation does not come as surprise considering that the processes of research software production, deployment and use involve typically multiple steps, platforms and engages several overlapping groups of people: researchers, developers and users .

Looking at the landscape from a preservation and sustainability perspective with a FAIR Software Route lens on, it appears that the chain of responsibilities to enable and implement FAIR Principles for research software even at a high level are distributed across the three groups of software platforms identified in the inventory. Therefore, the chain of responsibilities need to me maintained within and across the three layers (development, documentation, and preservation) to comply with the Principles. The current situation is at best of partial compliance with the FAIR Principles at any one of the three layers. The examples where FAIR principles are addressed for research software concern mostly the Findability (persistent identifiers, 'rich' metadata, indexed in searchable catalogues) or Accessibility (open, free and standardized protocol enabling authentication) and rarely Interoperability and Reusability (except for usage licences). This is again not surprising considering the early stages of FAIR Principles awareness and practice of sharing software compared to that of sharing data. It is also not appropriate to assess research software FAIRness based on the current FAIR Principles as these have a strong data-centric approach. A better approach should start with reviewing them from a software perspective and coming up with appropriate metrics to assess their FAIRness and also include other important aspects of sustainability such as long term preservation, curation and stewardship.

Decentralized or centralized FAIR route

Establishing a robust FAIR Software Route could follow the dominant decentralized model described earlier and its corollary distribution of responsibilities amongst several players. The decentralized route could for instance be proposed by recommending the use of best in class platforms for each of the three layers: 1) appropriate code hosting and development platforms such as for example GitHub.com , 2) appropriate domain or organizational software registries integrated with recommended code hosting platforms (like GitHub.com) to provide relevant domain contextual information and documentation including citations and links to academic publications, and 3) long-term storage archives for code preservations such as the Software Heritage archive which is now seamlessly integrated with GitHub.com.

To make this decentralized FAIR Software Route operational, it will be essential to provide in parallel additional recommendations for good practices to ensure that no gaps remain open between the three type of platforms and to achieve optimum and increasing compliance with the FAIR Principles for improved citability, discoverability and reusability. Examples of such recommendations of good practice are the provision and maintenance of a single and authoritative metadata file about the software in the repository on the code hosting platform, encouraging the use of software container technologies, and providing rich domain metadata in curated software registries. Examples of such recommendations are emerging and will need to be further developed such as the *Four simple recommendations to encourage best practices in research software*²⁵, the *Top 10 FAIR Data Things Research Software*²⁶, and the *Software Development Guide* developed by Netherlands eScience Center²⁷. Furthermore, to ensure practical implementation of the decentralized FAIR Software Route, measuring compliance and uptake of these recommendations should be performed using metrics that are specifically developed for software.

In this decentralized model, a critical weakness to be considered is the long-term sustainability of recommended platforms. The most widely used code hosting platform GitHub.com for example does not offer any guaranteed service level and could go down without prior notice which represents a potential single points of failure. It is also difficult to guarantee the long term sustainability of domain software registries or archives when most

²⁵ Jiménez RC, Kuzak M, Alhamdoosh M et al. Four simple recommendations to encourage best practices in research software [version 1; referees: 3 approved]. F1000Research 2017, 6:876 (<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11407.1>)

²⁶ <http://librarycarpentry.org/Top10FAIR/03-software/index.html>

²⁷ <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/expertise/software-development-guide>

of them are still running as projects. The sustainability of the decentralized FAIR Software Route would therefore require and depend on some sort of formal agreements between (at least some) platforms and services providers.

However, such formal agreements could be difficult to achieve in practice and a more centralized FAIR Software Route approach could be a practical and feasible alternative. A specific organization or groups of organizations from stakeholders such as research funders, research, technology and data stewardship organizations could realistically centralize into one infrastructure the three layers and their corresponding platforms. This approach would have the advantage of ensuring robust integration between the platforms in the three layers and facilitate the monitoring of FAIR uptake in software practices.

This is to some extent what the DOE CODE project tries to achieve by offering a software deposit route that includes an organizational Gitlab instance for code hosting (although this is in practice only for non public repositories rather than for improving sustainability) and a software registry which effectively integrates the “Development” layer with the “Documentation” layer in a single organization.

Organizations like KNAW-DANS and the NLeScience Center are very well positioned in The Netherlands to develop such an approach. The centralized or rather integrated approach would also echo the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) agenda for which several funded projects are already tackling parts of the sustainable software challenge²⁸.

Annex : FAIR Software Route Inventory

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/10AVwyu4RHd1MLusqBuh4iwbMclM5n_Zbe1a6Nsp_nZE/edit?usp=sharing

²⁸ See EOSC-HUB <https://eosc-hub.eu/>, EOSC-Pilot <https://eosc-pilot.eu/node> and FAIRsFAIR